

MAI-AI Questionnaire

Questionnaire answered by participants pre and post study, separated by constructs and showcasing differences between pre and post questions.

Construct	Question	Pre-study questionnaire	Post-study questionnaire
Attitudes	Q1	The use of AI makes me feel: Pessimistic (1) / Optimistic (5) about my future career prospects.	=
	Q2	I believe using AI for my studies is: Detrimental (1) / Beneficial (5) for my learning outcomes.	=
AI Engagement	Q3	I use AI tools (e.g.: ChatGPT, Gemini, Claude, Copilot) for my academic work.	N/A
	Q4	I use AI to help me understand concepts when studying.	I intend to use AI to help me understand concepts when studying.
	Q5	I use AI to help with brainstorming or generating new ideas for a task.	I intend to use AI to help with brainstorming or generating new ideas for a task.
	Q6	I use AI tools to find the information needed for my work.	I intend to use AI tools to find the information needed for my work.
	Q7	I use AI tools to check or verify my work before submission.	I intend to use AI tools to check or verify my work before submission.
	Q8	I intend to use AI tools in my academic work in the future.	=
	Q9	I am selective about when to use AI tools based on my learning goals.	I intend to be selective about when to use AI tools based on my learning goals.
	Q10	I want to learn more about how to effectively use AI for learning.	=
AI Literacy	Q11	I understand the basic principles of how AI systems work.	=
	Q12	I am confident in my ability to use AI tools effectively for my studies and/or work.	=
	Q13	I am aware of the different types of AI tools available and their capabilities.	=
	Q14	I am aware of the limitations and potential biases in AI systems.	=
	Q15	I know how to evaluate the quality and reliability of AI-generated outputs.	=
Metacognitive Awareness	Q17	I am aware of how AI usage affects my own thinking processes.	=
	Q18	I am conscious of how AI usage affects my memory and retention of information.	=
	Q19	I am aware of when I use AI to avoid challenging cognitive tasks.	=

	Q20	I am aware of how much I rely on AI while working on academic tasks.	=
	Q26	I can recognize when AI usage enhances versus hinders my learning.	=
Metacognitive Regulation	Q16	I decide how to approach a problem on my own before I ask an AI for a solution.	=
	Q21	I focus on understanding the information an AI tool provides, not just on getting an answer.	=
	Q22	I verify the accuracy of AI outputs before using them.	=
	Q23	If an AI tool gives me incorrect or unclear information, I try to solve the task on my own.	=
	Q24	After completing a task with AI, I evaluate what I have learned versus what the AI did for me.	=
	Q25	After completing a task with AI, I ask myself If I could have accomplished the task more effectively without using an AI tool.	=
Autonomy & Control	Q27	I feel control of my learning process when I use AI.	=
	Q28	I feel ownership of my work when I use AI.	=
	Q29	I limit my AI usage when I want to develop my own skills.	=

The equal “=” symbol means the question was identical in both pre and post questionnaires. Since Q3 was not relevant in the post questionnaire, it was not asked (N/A). Q16 and Q26 are sorted to be inside their constructs, instead of their order of appearance.